

The War to End All Wars: Popular Representations of History of the First World War in Video Games

Biswadeep Chakraborty

Abstract

This paper focuses on study of the popular representations of history of the First World War in video games. Despite a growing body of literature on the history of video games, scholars largely neglect the representations of history in the games. This paper traces the inherent historicity in the creation of World War I video games, as well as trying to reach an understanding of how popular medias like video games could persuade and shape the popular imagination in the public 'memory'.

Keywords: *Video Games, Historical Gaming, First World War, Popular Culture.*

Public history uses a wide variety of genres, which are different from those of the academic discipline [...] If we can identify and reflect upon this generic range, the whole phenomenon, including the means by which they develop their sense of the past, can be appreciated more fully.¹

There is a consensus among scholars that now in the twenty-first century more than at any point in human civilization, the sense of 'history' is in decline. We are living in a post-truth world where facts are no more influential in shaping public opinion but trumped-up stories and barefaced lies in the form of mindless forwards on internet platforms develop the sense of history in what Jürgen Habermas termed the *Öffentlichkeit* or the 'public sphere' which nowadays is also in the digital realm. This post-truth ecosystem attracts principally the individual 'emotion', elevates the idiosyncrasies and deprecates the academic thesis has profound insinuations on how 'history' is manufactured and fed to the common masses. There is a general trend among academicians to downplay this whole scenario and argue that the general public has no interest in history and thus have too little knowledge of their past to fall into these

propagandist traps. This downplaying is related to the traditional scholars and historians who throughout the previous decades often criticized and dismissed 'popular culture' and 'popular history'. These criticisms and dismissals are frequently based on 'valorization' as according to Gerald Strauss popular history 'use approaches which "valorize" popular groups or movements by bringing them onto the historical stage, taking them seriously and making them sound important.'² The implicit criticism here is that popular history elevates the insignificant as significant by not following sound academic historical method. So, the academic criticism of popular history is based upon two ideas, first public disinterest in the past and second the ways general masses gather history, which often are not based on the academic thesis. However, it is difficult to understand how general masses or the 'public' is not interested in history, as historical films, novels or television series etc. had always been the bestsellers and blockbusters. According to E. H. Carr history is 'an unending dialogue between the present and the past'.³ Robert A. Rosenstone argued that the very assumption that 'written history is the only possible way of understanding the relationship of past to present' is problematic as 'historians tend to use written works of history to critique visual history as if that written history were itself something solid and unproblematic.'⁴ So we cannot deny popular history by comparing it with academic form of history whose reach is far less than that of historical films or other visual media, although we can always question the actual historical authenticity or the credibility of popular historical mediums. For example, whether a film on the Peloponnesian War is depicting the actual historical events of the war fought between Athens and Sparta or being fictionalized can be questioned, although historical fiction is a well-established genre and can be availed if mentioned at the start.

In today's world, we are literally surrounded by two terms 'digital' and 'virtual' — the human civilization is engulfed by this realm, whether taking online classes or work from homes we are in the digital domain round the clock. And even when we are not studying or working, we are always connected to the world through technologies like smart-watches, smartphones etc. when on the move and through virtual AI assistants when relaxing at home. The so-called 'digital revolution' started with the personal computer technologies from the 1980's and cloud-computing technologies

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of the 2000's completely changed how we store and preserve, rather 'safeguard,' our data or information.⁵ That data includes 'histories' which are now stored and learned by the masses digitally. From the 1980s to the 1990s one of the major inductions in the realm of personal and cumulative entertainment was the 'video game', which by the end of 1990s with proper improvements and standardizations matured as one of the most popular forms of visual engagements apart from film and television. As video games reach maturity they become controversial due to their violent nature, as battle and fighting genres are to be found most popular. The imagery and narrative of death is an imminent part of any historical narrative of war or conflict, as it is the only constant truth about wars throughout human civilization. In the words of Carlo Ginzburg, 'A visual language based on the superlative of violent expression worked, as we have seen, as a distancing device, projecting the gruesome reality of [...] conquest into a remote mythological world.'⁶

Thus the video game representations of history and historical events became a major source of understanding and consuming the past or history in the public sphere. Initially, there was a notion that video games were meant for children or at best young adults but as this digital realm matured and expanded the industry think-tanks realized that majority of the consumers are between the ages of eighteen and thirty-four years i.e., a staggering thirty-eight percent.⁷ This changed the type and genres of games as the gaming studios and developers started focusing on more reality-based contents, among which the most popular was the historical battle genre. Despite a growing body of literature on the history of video games, scholars largely neglect the representations of history in the games. Research on the video game representations of history and historical events is a very recent inclination among the academic community and very few specific researches have been published. In this paper, I will discuss and analyze representations of the First World War in popular culture through video games.

The First World War or the Great War is one of the few such watershed moments in history which has a great effect on the popular imagination of the entire human race. Although the First World War was never quite so fertile a topic as World War II for the popular culture, yet there were nevertheless a large number of War Novels, Fictional works, War Memoirs,

Films and Video Games which were produced in last hundred years throughout the world. Popular culture is a culture based on the tastes of ordinary people rather than the educated elite, and it is the entirety of ideas, perspectives, attitudes, images, and other phenomena that are within the mainstream of a given culture that is heavily influenced by mass media, and this collection of ideas permeates the everyday lives of the society.⁸ First World War is the first war in human history which took on characteristics that served as a symbol of modern warfare and dictated the nature of the future modern wars till now. It was the first war where such a large number of troops were mobilized throughout the continents and visited horrific new experiences on the combatants and the civilians alike. The fact that this war was till then unparalleled in terms of its scale or apparatus and devastation, could be understood from its nomenclature. From the time of its start until the approach of the Second World War, the First World War was called simply the *Great War*, 'great' in terms of everything from the technological advances to the new modern forms of war like the *Trench warfare*⁹ to the new arms and ammunitions. The world had seen nothing like it, and it was the hope of the survivors that their war was the last on this earth and hence H. G. Wells termed it 'The war to end all wars'.¹⁰ The *Great War* lasted 1,568 days from 28th July 1914 to 11th November 1918, and was without any parallel. It brought to an end four dynasties, ignited revolution, and forged new nations. But being a disaster of its own kind, the First World War also became the precondition for future disasters like the Second World War, whose casualties numbered millions more.

Attempting to explore historical game epistemologies of the First World War would probably be an overambitious project for this paper, but I will try and analyze certain aspects as and when required. Jeremie Clyde, Howard Hopkins and Glenn Wilkinson in their joint paper 'Beyond the "Historical" Simulation' argued in favour of a 'gamic mode' of history focusing on the construction of historical narrative via procedural rhetoric which is primarily based upon AlunMunslow's theory of 'constructionist epistemology'¹¹ which assumes that reality, reference and representation works together to form history thus what video games need to become more scholarly or true to history are 'justifiable truths'.¹² Although this issue of 'justifiable truths' becomes very complicated considering the fact that there are certain historical events or wars that stirrup controversies when

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portrayed accurately in video games. As video games are not mere visual mediums like films but they are interactive visual media where consumers or users play an active part and interact with the history and events, incorporationssuch as the Nazi holocaust in the Second World War or for that matter the psychological horrors of the unending trench warfare of the First World War,in particular, are highly controversial. As a result, heavily edited versions of actual events where certain episodes become almost invisible were incorporated in the video games of the World Wars, although this wasnot the situation in other visual entertainment mediums such as television or films. Here in contrast to the 'historical truth', the very concept of 'justifiable truths' come into force where certain 'unjustifiable' events of history areomitted from the so called 'gamic mode of history'.¹³ So probably producing a video game that is contemplated as not respectful of the memories of the First World War would be a very risky proposition in theory due to the fact that unlike the Second World War the first war was much more dull and prolonged in terms of actions, partly because of the 'trench' warfare which produced physical as well as psychological horrors for the participants of the wars. The idea of 'historical truth' is central to Sigmund Freud's psychoanalysis theory centred on trauma;wherein the human memory of a certain event of horror or trauma, what Freud called 'intellectual feeling', returns as an isolated and repressed piece of truth in memory. The First World War thus lodges in popular memory as a straight timeline of horrors starting from 1914 to the Second World War and adds up to the inhumane Nazi holocaust, which makes this period in history a difficult period to recreate in video games with historical accuracy.

The first video game on the First World War was an arcade game¹⁴ developed by Atari Inc. titled *Red Baron* which was released in 1980. This was revolutionary in many ways as it popularized the first-person flight simulator games the consumer in the game plays as an ace First World War fighter pilot fighting from the side of the Allies power. Although based on a historic war, the gamehad no storyline pertaining to the actual events of the war, as the gameplay was divided into rounds. Neither the player could choose any other side than the Allies, which was set by default. The arcade games of the initial video game era wereotherwise simple as they were neither nuanced nor complex in terms of game-play but the decision on the developers' part to restrict the player to represent only the Allied powers

was a 'political' decision. As the western world even in the midst of the cold war in the 1980s was united on the representation of the two World Wars and restricted a video game player to represent the Central powers (Germany, Austria-Hungary, Bulgaria and the Ottoman Empire) in the First World War and the Axis powers (Germany, Italy, and Japan) in the Second World War as an unwritten rule. Following the innovations in technology by the end of the 1980s the era of 'personal-gaming' started in the 1990s giving rise to 'console' games and 'personal computer' or PC games. Video game developer Cinemaware in 1990 released a First World War video game titled *Wings* for the Amiga range of personal computer platform of Commodore International. This game had a mix of gameplay from air dog-fights to bombing missions; like *Red Baron* this game was also an aerial fighter game but had a bit of an action-oriented narrative and war atmosphere. But in this game also the player was restricted to representing only the Allied powers and no real aircraft used in the war was represented. So, in the early phase of video games we see that the representation of history was not primary objective of the game developers, mainly due to the limitations of technology.

Another key title in the evolution of the First World War video games was *History Line: 1914-1918*, developed by the German video game company Blue Byte which was released in 1992 comprising both single and double-player modes with 24 single playable campaigns and 12 double player campaigns. *History Line* was a Turn-based tactics (TBT) strategy video game. Being a TBT strategy game *History Line* was completely different from *Red Baron*, as unlike an arcade game this was a computer game and the gameplay includes vast maps of Europe covering almost all the actual historical battlefields of the First World War. Another different and unique aspect of the game was that the player could choose between representing Germany or France in the war. This aspect of choosing between Central and Allied powers was a distinctive feature of the game as even its future versions would not give that choice to the players until the twenty-first century. This game was unique because of another of its aspects which was its quality of historical accuracy as it was quite educative in terms of gameplay and storyline. The developers in the game manual noted that the most important aspects of the game were not the violent actual warlike acts but battle tactics and reasoning.¹⁵

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The game starts in 1914 showing graphics and information on the assassination of Archduke Franz Ferdinand of Austria, and reveals the most immediate cause of the conflict. As Germany invades France the lush green fields of Europe are depicted and eventually as the war progresses the transformation of the geography with barbed wires and horrendous lines of trenches on both sides are revealed. The player was responsible for taking actual tactical military decisions in the game and with each mission was briefed with historical facts of that particular period along with actual images along with contemporary news reports on the war. History Line is a perfect example how video games could represent history and historical events accurately, the developers of the game at Blue Byte in their game manual compared video games with other mediums of popular visual and textual mediums like films and comic books or graphic novels,

To those who insist that computer games are not a suitable medium for transmitting educational knowledge, we would simply point out the parallels to film and comics. A few decades ago, films and comics were invariably called "trash", "nonsense" and "idiotic rubbish"- today they are central to education and are regarded as art.¹⁶

The historical accuracy of History Line is unmatched to any other video game on the First World War, and there is no doubt that 'historical truths' here triumphed the 'justifiable truths' for sure. This game was far ahead of its time not in terms of graphics or visual effects but in terms of game's storyboard design and historical accuracies in game narratives. The game developers in the manual of the game noted that they developed the game to be historically accurate:

Never before has entertainment software been so consciously designed to present knowledge and facts to the player in a graphic manner. We have put a lot of effort into presenting the facts in an easily understood manner so as to guarantee historical accuracy.¹⁷

The campaign maps in the game were hexagonal grid in design which was sluggish in comparison to modern strategy games but the fact that two players could simultaneously play onsplit screen was a big thing considering other games of that era. The History Line was developed in Germany and there were severe restrictions in terms of depicting violence and certain symbols like Nazi swastika etc. in video games in Germany

which was lifted pretty recently by the German government.¹⁸ But back in the 1990s because of the regulations game developers and designers at Blue Byte avoided too much gore and violence. Although they noted in the game manual that not supporting violence doesn't mean compromising on historical authenticity in terms of facts and accuracy of events. History Line is unique among video games on First World War due to this very fact that the developers found a perfect balance between not too violent gameplay and representation of history accurately. The developers of the game in the manual argued that, 'all the people involved in developing the game abhor violence and its dreadful consequences in war. However, pacifism should not be used as an excuse to distort reality or conceal facts'.¹⁹

We must understand that History Line was a strategy video game which was developed literally out of the analogue era board games like monopoly and others; thus, comparing it with modern day first-person shooter (FPS) games would not be proper. This game in the history of video games on the First World War must be appreciated for other aspects such as not compromising on either historical accuracy or the game-play.

The first modern first-person shooter video game on the First World War was not developed until the end years of the twentieth century; in the meanwhile several unorthodox attempts were made in the First World War video game genre. For example, Japanese video game developer Konami released in 1994 a fantasy historical fiction game titled *Castlevania: Bloodlines* or 'BanpaiaKirâ' in Japanese for the Sega Genesis home video game platform. This game had an elaborate storyline in which the main protagonist was the niece of the fictional character Dracula, a Vampire named Elizabeth Bartley who according to the story of the game instrumented the start of the First World War to bring back Dracula from death. Castlevania became a huge success and a series of video games were developed later on the theme and storyline. But since the genre was historic-fiction, there was much less restrictions in terms of developing characters and storylines as there was no need to balance 'historical truth' and 'justifiable truth'.

In 1999 the first elaborate and nuanced modern video game on the First World War was developed by a Stockholm based Swedish video gamer

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developer named Refraction Games and was published by the American video game publisher Take-Two Interactive — the game was titled *Codename Eagle*. The *Codename Eagle* was unlike any other video game ever released on World War-I, it was a first-person shooter based on all three dimensions, land, water and air. Now for the first time, a nuanced and complex storyline was used, as the gameplay was not merely based on arcade-rounds but 'missions' with specific objectives pertaining to the war. And thereby for the first time arises the dilemma of what to include and what not from the actual horrors of the First World War. The concepts of 'historical truths' and 'justifiable truths' came into play. There are several aspects of modern warfare which are much more morally gore than the ancient and medieval sword fights and bare raw violence, the use of mustard gas or chemical weapons and the horrific life of the mundane trench warfare was the reality of the first world war, which were not at all suitable for reproduction in an interactive role-playing video game. Should the players decide upon the course of the war and use brutal industrial weaponry? Or should they be allowed to (re)live virtually the horrors of the trenches? To solve these moral and somewhat psychological aspects the developers brilliantly chose to bypass all these controversies and questions altogether, by inventing their own 'parallel universe' or 'alternate timeline'. The game *Codename Eagle* was set in an alternate universe where First World War was started by a young Russian Tsar at the start of the twentieth century, and a resistance forged between the Allied forces of the free nations of the world to stop and counter this aggression. According to the version of history in this alternate timeline, the Russian revolution never took place and neither Germany was responsible for the chaos. The game starts with a narration in Russian accented English male voice, which states,

We know for sure that there is such a thing as Time-Warp. We also know that time-warps create alternative timelines or if you wish parallel worlds. The latest of time-warps took place around the year 1900. When the old Tsar died his son Pietro inherited the whole mighty empire. The young Tsar ambitious and power-hungry confiscated the steel industry turning it into an incredibly effective war machine. The empire scientists developed weapons of power and destructive force never seen before. So the war began. The Tsar led his forces himself, first invading his neighbours and then in furious blitzkrieg his forces campaigned over the world creating chaos and destruction. Even though hope was hard to find in this age of

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brutal tyranny an alliance was formed by the free countries of the world. But there was a long way to go, many battles to be fought and great losses to face. This was a time for heroes.²⁰

The developers replaced the German empire as the evildoer of the First World War by the Tsar and the Russian empire. This move must be seen from the perspective of the cold war, as Germany no longer remained a threat to the Allied powers but the new adversary was the Communist Russia, although this game was released eight years after the downfall of the USSR but the very change in narrative had the flavours of the erstwhile cold war era. This game was a masterpiece in terms of gameplay; the player could take part in land battle missions along with air and naval missions. The graphics by the standard of previous First World War video games were far superior. The weapons and vehicles of land, sea and air were more or less designed with accuracy keeping the historic period in mind. The controversial parts of the war such as trench warfare and the use of chemical weapons were effectively omitted along with the actual historical events of the war. This was well justified as at the very beginning the narrator declared the theory of time-warp and alternate timelines or parallel universes.

Following the lead of *Codename Eagle*, the video game developers adopted counterfactualism when drawing up the historical period of the Great War. In 2002 a first-person shooter video game was developed by the French video game studio 4X Studios titled *Iron Storm*. Based on speculative fiction genre the plot was set in a parallel universe where the First World War never ended, and the player appeared in 1964 on the fiftieth year of the Great War. Here again, no choice was given to the player in terms of choosing sides and by default, the protagonist was set as an Allied soldier. In terms of historical accuracy, *Iron Storm* was a mixed bag as on one hand for the first time 'trench warfare' and the use of industrial chemical weapons like mustard gas etc. were used in the gameplay making it much more gore than any previous video game on the war, whereas on the other hand World War-II era weapons like rocket launchers and contemporary vehicles like helicopters etc. were used, confusing the historical sense of the war. Another major game on WWI which focuses on the aerial combat during the Great War is *Rise of Flight: The First Great Air War*; released in 2009. The timeline of *Rise of Flight* covers 1916 to

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1918. The included game map covers over 120,000 square kilometres of the Western Front, western Ukraine and the English Channel. The 3D map with many towns, rivers and 'aerodromes' was designed according to the historical maps and information from the war years of 1914-1918. Another game called *Warfare 1917* is a strategy game set during World War I, released in 2008. In this game, the player can participate from both the British and German sides and have to capture the no man's land and trenches in the WWI battlefields, while fighting programmed enemies.²¹ One popular strategic WWI video game on the mobile platform which focuses on the trench warfare of WWI is called *Trenches*, which was released in 2009. The player is put into the role of the Battlefield Commander for the British Expeditionary Forces in Western Europe during 1914 against the German Army, or vice versa. The game spans throughout the war as the game progresses. This game somewhat corrected the historicity in the WWI games, it portrayed somewhat accurately the gore environment of the war trenches and accurately portrayed the dull negative environment of the battlefields with barbed wires and land mines. Although the balance between historical facts and excess violence is of the game *History Line* was very much missing, thus the game was rated and deemed only fit for adults. Another game, a submarine simulation set during WWI, the 1914 *Shells of Fury* offers a submarine technology from WWI (when submarines for the first introduced,) to the player or user. In *Shells of Fury*, the player commands one of four submarines manned by the Germans, including a tiny vessel whose primary armament was a scant two torpedoes and a much larger gasoline-powered sub that became the template for WWII sub fleets. One can play historical missions or a long campaign.²²

Video games changed very much post 2010 in the second decade of the twenty-first century with the advent of much powerful game engines and graphics cards, the attention detail became much more important than anything else in the games. Games like *Battlefield*, became less dependent historically on the First World War and adopted the war as a mere overall 'theme'. So the gameplay was thematically WWI but apart from peripheral details of the war such as accurate weaponry etc. historicity was overall neglected. So the technology of the computer graphics and computer-generated imagery evolved in the starting years of the twenty-first century

demanded for more realistic games which forced the video game developers and publishers to develop accurate historical period specific weaponry and attires and omitting actual history of the battles and timelines and more importantly the strategies. As historian Niall Ferguson noted that 'To the historian, in any case, tactics and the individual soldier's battlefield experience are only some of the war's many facets. Of more importance by far is the question of strategy.'²³

The modern battles and warfare of the twentieth century forced the video game developers into an incongruous situation where they had moral wrongdoings and act of brutality in one hand and corporeality of abomination on the other as we discussed earlier. The question was how from this setting an engaging yet non-objectionable video game would emerge? The video game developers quickly turned towards alternate-reality and counterfactualism or counterfactual-history. They started with the very question 'what if?' — and that gave them enough space to work in the actual environment of the war with all historical period specific details like costumes or attires and weaponry to retain the player's attention and engagement but in the hindsight omitting problematic historical episodes and war scenarios. Bruce Campbell Shelley the designer and developer of the famous *Age of Empires* video game series argued regarding historical video games that,

We're creating a commercial product here, a game that we'd like to appeal to a lot of people. Creating a truly accurate historical videogame would not only touch on areas we'd rather not deal with, in the end it just wouldn't be any fun.²⁴

So we can understand that neither video game producers and developers nor the consumers desired actual authentic storyline in a historical war game but on the other hand they would demand history specific appendages such as authentic war environments, weaponry, attires and so on. If we look at the actual historical events pertaining to the First World War we will understand that unlike the Second World War, the first war was very slow paced and dull in its entirety on both western and eastern fronts. The basic idea behind the trenches and fields of barbed wire was to slow down the attacking armies. A video game with no fighting for days and months but guarding the lines in the trenches would not appeal to anyone. Thus a video game which would accurately recreate the battle situations

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and war environments would be equally dull as well as achingly disturbing to the consumers. Although this is not correct in its entirety, this argument was nothing but to keep any controversies on the highly debated war and its atrocities at bay. In recent times several to the point accurate video games were developed and published over internet gaming platforms such as Stream on the First World War, such as *Verdun: 1914-1918*, which creates a niche genre of realistic video games with accurate portrayal of history. The game *Verdun: 1914-1918* developed by M2H Game studio and Blackmill Games, defined the very word 'realistic' in the WWI video games, with an accurate portrayal of battlefields and giving the choice of selecting either the Central powers or the Allied powers. Named after the battle of Verdun fought between February and December 1916 on the western front, the peripheral accuracies like military attires and weaponry were also kept in mind along with the dull environment of the trenches and the frontlines. *Verdun* was succeeded by a sequel *Tannenberg: Eastern Front 1914-1918*, named after the famous battle of Tannenberg fought in August 1914 between Russia and Germany on the eastern front.

Historian Niall Ferguson argued that historical video games based on First or Second World Wars must not be seen as an attempt to make the history relevant to today's generation but as an attempt to revitalize that episode of human history through technology. According to Ferguson when the current and future generations would like to understand a certain period they might not turn pages of the history books but instead (re)live that period of history through the video games, which in turn might help them take better strategic decisions in real life,

Gaming history is not a crass attempt to make the subject relevant to today's kids. Rather it's an attempt to revitalize history with the kind of technology that kids have pioneered. And why not? After all, the Game Boy generation is growing up. And, as they seek a deeper understanding of the world we live in, they may not turn first to the bookshelves. They may demand to playor rather replaythe great game of history for themselves. And who knows? When they come to make real strategic decisions, maybe this strategically savvy generation will do a better job than we did.²⁵

Hence we can see that, popular media can be extremely effective in persuading and shaping the popular imagination in a way to deconstruct the putatively unified narrative of a particular historical event or a

watershed moment in history, like in this case the First World War. That in turn shapes the popular culture. Thus study of the representations of history of the First World War in video games is important to understand the paradoxical ambivalence which should not be forgotten that individual memory makes the past closer; social memory makes it more distant.²⁶ Therefore we can conclude on the very point that representation of history through video games in this case history of the First World War must not be seen in vacuum, but in connection to 'memory' and 'distance'. The historical video games on the First World War don't replace traditional academic history books on the subject as a matter of fact they were never supposed to. Instead, these interactive and highly sophisticated games create a new space in representation of history out of the textual basis into the immersive role-playing digital realm attempting to reinvigorate the history of the Great War.

Endnotes :

- ¹ Ludmilla Jordanova, *History in Practice* (London: Arnold, 2000), p.153.
- ² William Beik, 'The Dilemma of Popular History', *Past & Present* 141 (1993): 207-215, pp.209-10.
- ³ E. H. Carr, *What is History?* (London: Penguin Books, 1990), p.30.
- ⁴ Robert A. Rosenstone, *Visions of the Past: The Challenge of Film to Our Idea of History* (Cambridge, MA and London, UK: Harvard University Press, 1995), p.49.
- ⁵ Biswadeep Chakraborty, 'Safeguarding the Information of Audio Heritage in the Digital Age: A Case Study on Sound Archiving', *Navajyoti International Journal of Multi-Disciplinary Research* 3.2 (2019):1-9. <https://bit.ly/3AZYgxg> Accessed: 20.06.2020.
- ⁶ Carlo Ginzburg, *Fear Reverence Terror: Five Essays in Political Iconography* (Calcutta: Seagull Books, 2017), p.33.
- ⁷ J. Clement, *Distribution of video gamers in the United States in 2020, by age group*, Statista, 2021, <https://www.statista.com/statistics/189582/age-of-us-video-game-players-since-2010> Accessed 18.05.2021.
- ⁸ Gary West, *What Is Pop Culture?*, Mr. Pop Culture / Mr. Timeline. <http://mrpopculture.com/what-is-pop-culture>. Accessed: 18.06.2020.
- ⁹ Trench warfare is a type of combat in which opposing troops fight from trenches facing each other. Trench warfare occurred when a revolution in

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- firepower was not matched by similar advances in mobility, resulting in a gruelling form of warfare in which the defender held the advantage. The most famous use of trench warfare is the Western Front in World War I. On the Western Front in 1914–18, both sides constructed elaborate trench and dugout systems opposing each other along a front, protected from assault by barbed wire. See Nicholas Murray, *The Rocky Road to the Great War: The Evolution of Trench Warfare to 1914* (Washington D.C.: Potomac Books, 2013).
- ¹⁰ During August 1914, immediately after the outbreak of the war, British author and social commentator H. G. Wells published a number of articles in London newspapers that subsequently appeared as a book entitled *The War That Will End War*. See W. Warren Wagar, *H.G. Wells: Traversing Time* (Middletown, CT: Weleyan University Press, 2004).
- ¹¹ See Alun Munslow, *Narrative and History: Theory and History* (New York: Palgrave Macmillan, 2007).
- ¹² Jeremie Clyde, Howard Hopkins and Glenn Wilkinson, 'Beyond the "Historical" Simulation: Using Theories of History to Inform Scholarly Game Design', *The Journal of the Canadian Game Studies Association* 6.9 (2012): 3-16.
- ¹³ For example, in almost all video games on WWII the Nazi holocaust which is considered a 'historical truth' is always missing from the storyline, whereas other minor war atrocities by the Nazis like the "Commissar Order" might be included in the game-play.
- ¹⁴ Introduced originally in the 1970s an arcade game is generally installed in public spaces such as video game parlours and other playing arcades, where the general public could play the games by paying a nominal amount. Arcade gaming was popular before the advent of the personal gaming platforms and eventually died as personal game platforms such as Nintendo and PC gaming became mainstream.
- ¹⁵ Basing a game of strategy on the terrible First World War is a daring enterprise. However, the most important features of the game are not warlike acts but tactical reasoning and entertainment value. Historyline: 1914-1918 - Game Manual. <https://www.lemonamiga.com/games/docs.php?id=798>. Accessed: 20.06.2020.
- ¹⁶ Historyline: 1914-1918 - Game Manual.
- ¹⁷ Historyline: 1914-1918 - Game Manual.
- ¹⁸ 'Germany lifts total ban on Nazi symbols in video games'. BBC News, 10 August 2018. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-45142651>. Accessed: 20.06.2020.
- ¹⁹ History line: 1914-1918 - Game Manual.
- ²⁰ Codename Eagle. For Windows PC, Refraction Games, 1999.
- ²¹ *Warfare 1917 Review*, Jay is Games. 16 December, 2008. <http://>

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jayisgames.com/review/warfare_1917.php/Accessed: 16.06.2020.

- ²² Breeden, John, 'This Sub Game Is Out of Its Depth', *The Washington Post*, Friday, February 1, 2008. <http://www.washingtonpost.com/wp-dyn/content/article/2008/01/31/AR20080131011171pf.html>. Accessed: 16.06.2020.
- ²³ Niall Ferguson, 'How to Win a War', *New York Magazine*, Oct. 12, 2006. <https://nymag.com/news/features/2>. Accessed: 16.06.2020.
- ²⁴ Bruce Shelley, in Rausch, Allen 'Delsyn'. 'Art & Design: The Alternate History of Age of Empires III (PC)', in Gamespy, Oct. 14, 2005. <http://uk.pc.gamespy.com/pc/age-of-empires-iii/658725p1.html>. Accessed: 19.06.2020.
- ²⁵ Ferguson, 'How to Win a War'.
- ²⁶ Ginzburg, *Fear Reverence Terror*, p.33.